

MOTHER TONGUE IN THEIR CLASSES WISE WORDS WITH WORK THROUGH SPEECH TO GROW METHODOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

This in the article wise words , speech cultivation , speech of growing up methods about data brought

KEYWORDS

In education reforms , language , wisdom words , speech to grow methods

INTRODUCTION

Education in the system reforms , fundamentally updates and State language about the law students speech formation , in particular , is large age students speech grow up methodology and in practice changes to be requirement is enough These changes normative educational method in the literature certain level own on the contrary found The same at the time to them present requirements the point in terms of critical approach demand will be done .

MAIN PART

Many people scientists school of students speech grow up conditions right they emphasize . Theirs according to the speech of culture low student to personality negative effect shows . Classmates between stratification surface will come This is especially a son in children more is observed . Peers with in communication lazy , manly , careless being remains . From this except that in students surroundings to learn has been interest decreases later while at school lessons master not to get reason will be Announcement done research their work summarizing learned without their in most of them school age in students speech culture to form about tasks solution to do relatively as follows the only one approach necessity we determined :

- in the student speech to hear skill formation , pronunciation while later perfect if occupied will be
- _ sure pronunciation harvest to do , that is short and understandable from words usage : the word _ pronunciation when you do accent right to put on work
- _ of speech expressiveness formation (of speech natural , free , that is of speech conscious expressed) ;
- _ speech to hear skills formation ;
- _ own his opinion free and consistent statement reach qualification formation

From researchers L. P. Fedorenko and GAFomichevalar Methodical in terms of important the idea before they push : " The child. " to the speech to teach , " he writes they , him language matter (speech organs exercise make) language symbols , lexicon and grammar characters (intellect exercise to make) meaning to understand facilitation , lexicon and grammar

characters using existence assessment express teaching , literature standards to remember to facilitate help to give means " .

Literary language concept wide comprehensive , many edged is an event . Literary language development stability in providing of children from youth speech cultures content find and bring up should. Language of laws to education application relationship with students in teaching methods right application (visualization , distribution given on assignment papers with work ways knowing) methods to be improved. Especially, mother language that's it in class methods right apply get big important have Primary from grade to 5th grade past of the student in his speech disadvantages to be natural Mother tongue Textbook (grade 5 mother tongue . Tashkent-2020) topics from phonetics starting (pronunciation and spelling norms , lexicology , punctuation) work papers on up to performance organic connected topics with get to know through oral and written speeches forming they go

" **Language belongs to the nation they say** . This is the eye gard-guborl from from dust zones seconds as clean up to go each one of us ing child -

lik , citizenship it is our duty . Language our own ing , of our own , to himself wait - the main symbol of our league . " Language belongs to the nation it is called the spirit . Language if it disappears

the nation is complete will be Language if he lives , the nation will also live ." TORA SULAYMON [3]

Muhammad Yusuf's "Mother Tongue "

What if not you ? to us smooth poems ,

" In **this world language there is no the heart no** " , they say .

Rate it giving gone Alishers ,

My heart in the net unfading my flower

mother tongue , sorry me , mother language .[4]

Mind to evil if you look at it , it's a person razil , mak blind , deceitful

be remains . (Abu Nasr Farabi) [8]

Nature to whom intelligence , knowledge if he gives , he is good affairs to do shake hands. (Yusuf Khos Hajib) [9]

Human the most honorable i and great level his is smart .

(Abdurauf Fitrat)[9]

If you are human, you are not human.

It is the grief of the people who do not have their own. (Alisher Navoi) [17]

your tongue he is safe start

Say the word availa , it will be extended be young (Yusuf Khos Hajib) [27]

Knowledge return , repeat is a fruit . (Beruni) Za -

cot the rule If so , greatness will be Knowledge in whom if so , great

will be (Yusuf Khos Hajib) Knowledge with happiness way opens ,

that's it according to learned Be happy the way the search (Ahmed Yugnakiy)

What you don't know ask learned - scientist , do n't ask shyly -

gan - to himself tyrant (tyranny doer). (Alisher Navoi) Kishikim

Science is science It is known to the people it 's good . (Abdullah Awlani)

[52]

of the book the number not his the better benefit brings

(Cicero, Greek) Literate be standing up book didn't read

person's illiterate the difference no (Mark Twain, English)

Good this is a book my in my life important one event

(Stendhal, French) Books wisdom to spread

is a weapon . (John Comenius, Polish) [60]

It's early to stand custom do Har my man the sun until it comes out in sleep if there is , sustenance less be (" Nightmare ") Honesty a person great ones level delivers (Alisher Navoi) Mouth and of the tongue decoration right is a word , a word right speak your heart decoration (Ahmed Yugnakiy) Enmity no , the fair horse wins. (Amir Temur) Friendship is human the most excellent quality (Oybek) Love , friend love doesn't know the border (Mirtemir) [66-67] In the textbook cited wise words topic scope and compact the fact that the student is interested .

Eastern thinkers and world philosophers	Subject name
Alisher Navoi	Language , manners , humanity
Abdulla Avloni	Education
Amir Temur	Power , knowledge , justice
Ahmad Yugnaki	That's right vocabulary
Oybek	Friendship
Mirtemir	Kindness
" Nightmare "	It's early to stay
John Comenius	Book
Mark Twain	Literate to be
Cicero	Good book
Stendhal	Book
Yusuf Khos Hajib	The language guard
Beruni	Knowledge
Muhammad Zehni	Politeness , manners , intelligence
Abdurauf Phytrate	Mind
Abu Nasr Farabi	Insidiousness , wickedness
Muhammad Yusuf	Language
Right Solomon	Language

CONCLUSION

Students speech development and to them mother language teach in the field psychological and pedagogical studies analysis to do the following to conclusions to arrive enable gives:

- Speech development is individual student in development central place possessor socio-historical the experience to master about very complicated and a lot factorial is a process.
- It is spontaneous process not but pedagogical leadership offer doer creative is a process. The student's speech development process manager pedagogue this process laws, mechanisms and his different young stages features knowledge , speech individual characteristics of development according to to know and of the student to himself typical features account received without his to the speech pedagogical effect of showing the most efficient ways to choose a must Teachers student speech redevelopment methods apply get them interesting get it , fluently speech to speak to teach need

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